

The Burden and Awareness of Hepatitis C Virus Infection among the Patient Attending OPD in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Bihar**Ankur Kumar¹, Sanjay Nag², Ramesh Prasad Singh³**¹SMO and Infection Control Officer, Department of Central Pathology, BMIMSH Pawapuri, Bihar, India²Associate Professor, Department of Microbiology, ANMM College and Hospital Gaya, Bihar, India³Tutor, Department of Microbiology, ANMM College and Hospital Gaya, Bihar, India

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Corresponding author: Dr. Ankur Kumar

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection prevalence is believed to be elevated in Bihar, India; however, state-wide prevalence data are not available. An understanding of HCV prevalence, risk factors and genotype distribution can be used to plan control measures in Bihar.**Material & Method:** A prospective, OPD-based serosurvey was conducted from March-2024 to October-2024 at ANMMCH Gaya, Bihar. Children aged ≥ 5 years and adults were eligible to participate. Demographic and risk behavior data were collected, and serological specimens were obtained and tested for anti-HCV antibody.**Result:** 8767 OPD patients participated in the study shows anti-HCV prevalence of 0.27%. Anti-HCV positivity was most prevalent in the 40–49 year-old and 30–39 year-old age groups (33.33% and 25.0% respectively). Sex wise distribution shows that there was slight male preponderance (58%). Out of total number of positive cases (24), 14 (58.33%) were males and 10 (41.66%) were females. Among all positive cases having a history of Diabetes, tuberculosis, Chronic Renal Failure and Cancer were 3.15%, 3.94%, 0.79% and 0.79% respectively.**Conclusion:** The study findings, including the overall prevalence of chronic HCV infection, associated risk factors and demographic characteristics can guide prevention and control efforts, including treatment provision. In addition to high-risk populations, efforts targeting rural areas and adults aged would be the most effective for identifying infected individuals.**Keywords:** HCV, Anti-HCV antibody, Seroprevalence.

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Introduction

There are an estimated 70 million people living with hepatitis C Virus (HCV) infection around the world [1]. Persons living with HCV infection are at risk of developing liver cirrhosis and progressing to end stage liver disease and liver cancer (hepatocellular carcinoma). Globally, an estimated 700,000 people die annually due to complications related to HCV infection [2].

The World Health Organization (WHO) has set ambitious targets to eliminate HCV infection as a public health problem by 2030(3). In order to achieve these targets, which include reduction of new infections by 90% and deaths by 65%, there is a need to increase prevention strategies and access to treatment. Treatment for HCV has improved dramatically with the addition of direct acting antivirals (DAAs), which are easy to take oral regimens that are highly effective, have minimal side effects, and achieve cure rates of over 90% [4,5]. In order to establish effective prevention and treatment programs, there is a need to understand

the epidemiology and burden of disease in the country or community. However, such data are lacking in many countries, particularly in lower and middle income countries which shoulder most of the burden [6]. There are significant geographical variations in prevalence patterns and genotype distribution globally [6,7], with populations in North America and Western Europe having anti-HCV prevalence rates generally less than 1%, while in some areas of Asia and the Middle East, prevalence rates exceed 5% [1,6,7,8,9].

In India, where genotype 3 is thought to be most common [10], population based studies on HCV infection prevalence are lacking, and the epidemiology is not well described. Some studies from India suggest the HCV prevalence may be low, however, there are significant variations within regions and sub-populations, with some studies demonstrating very high prevalence rates [9,11]. Population HCV seroprevalence data are lacking in Bihar, a state in North-eastern India.

Epidemiological assessment of the burden of disease and related risk factors in the state are essential for public health planning strategies to combat this disease. This study assessed the prevalence of HCV infection in Bihar and identify risk factors associated with the disease.

Aims and Objectives

From the study we had conclude about -

- To estimate the seroprevalence of anti-HCV antibody among the patient attending in OPD of ANMCH Gaya, Bihar situated at north-eastern state of India.
- To know associated risk factors and their demographic characteristics.
- To help policy makers for formulating appropriate control strategies against Hepatitis C virus.

Materials and Methods

Type of Study -This was a hospital lab based prospective study.

Period of study - Study conducted from March 2024 to October 2024 (7 months).

Place of study - Microbiology department, ANMCH Gaya.

Age: Children aged ≥ 5 years and adults were eligible to participate in this study.

Gender: No gender specification.

Methodology:

2ml blood sample was drawn in a serum separator tube from patient attending OPD who were visited first time in ANMCH Gaya, Bihar irrespective of previous anti-HCV status, after taking consent from patient, or from his/her parents if he/she not able to give consent. These samples collected at sample collection unit and sent to Microbiology department for further study. Within one hour of collection, the samples were centrifuged for 15

minutes at 3,000 revolutions per minute and were tested for anti-HCV antibody. Unused blood was disposed of as per healthcare waste management guidelines and all specimens were destroyed following completion of the study.

Demographic and risk behavior data were also collected by survey questionnaire, after obtaining informed consent. The study questionnaire was administered as a face-to-face interview and if needed by telephonic mode also about socio-demographic data, medical history, lifestyle information.

Data Analysis & Results

There were a total of 8767 samples collected from different OPD attending patients who agreed to participate in the study.

Different results and socio-demographic characteristics of this study were analysed and shown in Table (1-5) and Figure (1-5).

Out of 8767 OPD patients tested 24 were found positive for anti-HCV antibody and shows the prevalence of anti-HCV antibody. The overall prevalence of anti-HCV was 0.27% ($8767/24 \times 100$) as shown in Figure 1.

Anti-HCV antibody positivity was most prevalent in the 40–49 year-old and 30–39 year-old age groups (33.33% and 25.00% respectively) as shown in Table 1 and Figure 3. The mean age of positive patients was 42.9 years with the majority (approx 33%) of positive cases in the 40–49 years age group as shown in Figure 3. Sex wise distribution shows that there was slight male preponderance. Out of total number of positive cases (24), 14 (58.33%) were males and 10 (41.66%) were females as shown in Figure 2.

In this study among all positive cases having a history of Diabetes, hypertension, Chronic Renal Failure and Cancer were 8.33%, 12.50%, 4.16% and 8.33% respectively as shown in Table 2-5.

Figure 1: Seropositivity of anti-HCV antibody

Demographic characteristics and risk factors associated among anti-HCV seropositive patients (n=24) described in Figure (2-3) and Table (1-5)

Figure 2: Distribution of anti-HCV seropositive cases according to sex n=24

Table 1: Distribution of anti-HCV seropositive cases according to Age group n=24

Age Group (years)	HBsAg positive n (%)
5-18	01 (4.16%)
19-29	02 (8.33%)
30-39	06 (25.00%)
40-49	08 (33.33%)
50-59	05 (20.83%)
>=60	02 (8.33%)

Figure 3: Comparison of anti-HCV positivity with different Age group

Table 2: Distribution of anti-HCV seropositive cases according to Diabetes status n=24

Diabetes status	N (%)
Yes	02 (8.33%)
No	22 (91.66%)

Table 3: Distribution of anti-HCV seropositive cases according to Hypertension status n=24

Hypertension status	N (%)
Yes	03 (12.50%)
No	21 (87.50%)

Table 4: Distribution of anti-HCV seropositive cases according to Chronic Renal Failure status n=24

Chronic Renal Failure	N (%)
Yes	01 (4.16%)
No	23 (95.83%)

Table 5: Distribution of anti-HCV seropositive cases according to Cancer status n=24

Cancer status	N (%)
Yes	02 (8.33%)
No	22 (91.66%)

Discussion

This study, the first assessing the prevalence and risk factors for HCV infection in Gaya region of Bihar, India. We found an overall prevalence of anti-HCV is 0.27%. We found that males and persons aged 40-49, had the greatest odds of being infected with HCV.

Another previous studies in 2014 from Punjab [12] showing the association of HCV with age, sex and rural residence has been observed, noting the increasing prevalence with age, it would be tempting to consider that transmission risk has decreased over time and younger people are at lower risk, however, the youngest age groups studied, 5±18 and 19±29 year olds, had HCV seropositive rates of over 1% and 2% respectively, suggesting that transmission risk persists in Punjab, which is similar pattern as our study. Testing for incident HCV and HBV cases is only supported by the country's national Integrated Disease Surveillance Programme (IDSP) in outbreak situations [13]. Fortunately, treatment costs for HCV infection in India have decreased significantly with the introduction of direct acting antiviral drugs in 2015, which have proven to be highly effective [14].

This study, help in assessing the prevalence of anti-HCV antibody in Gaya region of Bihar state. But this study is subject to several limitations such as, we were not able to independently verify any of the responses on the questionnaire. Also, we could not determine the number of nonresponders. As with any cross-sectional study that examines a chronic condition, it is challenging to attribute risk due to lack of temporality, as the HCV infection could have occurred at any time during the lifetime of the study subjects. The sampling method of this study, which included patient attending in OPD of

ANMMCH Gaya, could lead to potential selection bias. Persons living together are more likely to exhibit similar behaviors and could lead to disproportionate risks in the sample that may not be representative of the general population.

Additionally, the sampling method of our study was not designed to produce precise per-region prevalence estimates; there was a preponderance of patient attending in OPD of ANMMCH Gaya were found to have a high prevalence of HCV than general residents. Thus these results should be interpreted with caution, as this could lead to overestimation of the prevalence in these areas.

Conclusion

The data presented in this study will provide a baseline for planning purposes and will help get an initial understanding of HCV disease burden in Gaya region of Bihar. In order to monitor the trends and spread of Hepatitis C, we intent to collect robust data at regular intervals for better understanding of the epidemiology of Hepatitis C.

Proposed Program Implementation Strategy as per the analysis Focused interventions (awareness, screening, and treatment services) are required in these areas for Hepatitis C prevalence study.

Need to establish an inbuilt component of continuous surveillance as a part of the program through existing mechanisms.

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